

Data Management Plan for "Unequal Shadows: Informality, Kinship and Tax Morale in Latvia"

Version 1

Description

The data management plan is developed within the project 'Unequal Shadows: Informality, Kinship and Tax Morale in Latvia' (Izp-2025/1-0346) (project manager: Andris Saulītis, 01.01.2026. – 31.12.2028).

The project aims to understand how the shadow economy functions in conditions of high economic inequality and to develop policy recommendations for an effective tax system that can reduce both inequality and the shadow economy. By integrating insights from economics, sociology, and public policy, the project will deliver both scientific and practical contributions of relevance to Latvia and similar countries.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grant

Unequal Shadows: Informality, Kinship and Tax Morale in Latvia (Izp-2025/1-0346-v2)

Researchers

Andris Saulitis (0000-0002-5328-7645), Alise Krūmiņa (0009-0007-0740-5149), Lilith Burgstaller (0000-0003-3174-1883), Arnis Sauka (0000-0002-7708-4375), Talis Putnins (0000-0001-5731-499X)

Organizations

University of Latvia, Baltic International Centre for Economic Policy Studies (BICEPS)

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: Data Management Plan for "Unequal Shadows: Informality, Kinship and Tax Morale in Latvia"

Description:

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Organizations:

University of Latvia

Baltic International Centre for Economic Policy Studies (BICEPS)

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2. Funding

Funding organizations: Latvian Council of Science | | LCS

Grants: Unequal Shadows: Informality, Kinship and Tax Morale in Latvia (lzp-2025/1-0346-v2)

Project:

3. License

License: [CC-BY-4.0](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

Publication Date:

4. Templates

Descriptions

Firm-level survey data

A dataset based on surveys about Baltic firm involvement in the shadow economy, developed by Putniņš and Sauka (2015), i.e., the Shadow Economy Index for the Baltic countries. Multiple survey questions address tax evasion and tax morale based on various scales.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The purpose of the survey data collection is to assess the involvement of Baltic firms in the shadow economy. It was developed by Putniņš and Sauka in 2015. This data set will be combined with financial information from the Orbis firm database.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Survey data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

CSV

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

10

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.6 If No, please describe, if you have considered re-using any of existing data?

No

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The dataset will be valuable for researchers studying shadow economy and development economics. It will also be useful for Latvian policymakers and financial sector institutions seeking evidence on how informality affects access to credit and firm growth. In addition, the findings may inform analyses conducted by international organisations such as the European Commission and the OECD, contributing to broader policy discussions on financial development and economic transparency in the Baltic region.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

DDI (Data Documentation Initiative)

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

DataverseLV

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

Yes. The dataset will be handled in formats that are open, machine-readable, and suitable for use in standard statistical and data-processing software. The working dataset will be stored in widely used formats such as CSV and compatible formats for statistical packages (e.g., SPSS, Stata and R), ensuring that they can be readily accessed, processed, and analysed across different software environments.

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

No

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Arnis Sauka (0000-0002-7708-4375)

3.1.3 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR after project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Encryption
- Passwords
- Physical access control

Survey data will be protected through a combination of password security, encryption, and physical access controls. All digital files will be stored on secure, password-protected systems, with access limited to authorized research team members. Strong, regularly updated passwords and, where possible, multi-factor authentication will be used to prevent unauthorized access. Data will be encrypted both in transit and at rest using industry-standard encryption protocols to ensure confidentiality.

Physical access to any devices or storage media containing survey data will be restricted to secure locations, such as locked offices or cabinets within controlled-access buildings. Only authorized personnel will have access to these spaces. Together, these measures ensure that survey data remain secure, confidential, and protected against unauthorized access or loss.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

The collection and use of survey data on firms' participation in the shadow economy will adhere to strict ethical standards to protect respondents and ensure responsible research practices. Participation will be voluntary, and respondents will be fully informed about the purpose of the study, the types of data collected, and how the data will be used. Informed consent will be obtained prior to data

collection, and respondents will have the right to decline to answer any question or withdraw from the study at any time without consequences.

Given the sensitive nature of the topic, particular care will be taken to ensure confidentiality and anonymity. Identifiable information will be minimized. Data will be reported only in aggregated form, preventing the identification of individual firms.

Data sharing will follow ethical and legal guidelines, ensuring that any shared datasets are anonymized and stripped of identifying details. Access to such data will be restricted to legitimate research purposes. These measures aim to minimize risks to participants while enabling valuable insights into the shadow economy.

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

No

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Online experiment data

To empirically address the links among inheritance taxation, kinship networks, and tax morale an online laboratory experiment will be employed to simulate intergenerational wealth transfers under varying tax and audit regimes.

The participants will be recruited online labor market platforms or pollster companies to access a demographically diverse sample. Participants will engage in public goods games across simulated generations, allowing us to observe how the presence or absence of inheritance taxation and various levels of income tax, as well as the probability and severity of audits, affect both declared transfers and tax morale. Each session simulates intergenerational transfers within kinship groups, using a public goods game framework to model

real-world decisions about wealth sharing and tax compliance.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The online experiment data is collected to investigate how the inheritance taxation design and perceptions thereof affect the compliance behavior and attitudes towards redistribution. Particularly, to analyze these links in a context of informal kinship-based systems that substitute for formal institutional arrangements.

The online experiment is designed to address the dynamics among inheritance taxation, kinship networks, and tax morale to investigate how they shape intergenerational wealth transfers and inequality.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Experimental data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

CSV

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

10

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The data might be useful to researchers studying behavioral economics, public policy, sociology, psychology and others. It will be particularly useful for policymakers and tax authorities in Latvia, who are designing or reforming inheritance taxation in contexts where informal practices and family networks play a central role in economic life. Furthermore, the dataset can be used by international organizations that assist states in developing fair and effective taxation systems.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

DDI (Data Documentation Initiative)

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

DataverseLV

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

Yes

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.2 Are the data usable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Encryption
- Passwords
- Physical access control

Data will be protected through a combination of password security, encryption, and physical access controls. All digital files will be stored on secure, password-protected systems, with access limited to authorized research team members.

Strong, regularly updated passwords and, where possible, multi-factor authentication will be used to prevent unauthorized access. Data will be encrypted both in transit and at rest using industry-standard encryption protocols to ensure confidentiality.

Physical access to any devices or storage media containing survey data will be restricted to secure locations, such as locked offices or cabinets within controlled-access buildings. Only authorized personnel will have access to these spaces. Together, these measures ensure that survey data remain secure, confidential, and protected against unauthorized access or loss.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Nationally representative survey data

The nationally representative survey (n>1300) is designed to assess public attitudes and behaviors related to the shadow economy and inequality. This survey will specifically measure the prevalence and social acceptance of informal practices identified through anthropological fieldwork, such as envelope wages, unregistered employment, and kinship-based mutual aid, thereby enabling a robust assessment of their actual impact on Latvian society and socioeconomic stratification.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The survey data is collected to assess public attitudes and behaviors related to shadow economy and inequality. This survey will specifically

measure the prevalence and social acceptance of informal practices identified through anthropological fieldwork, such as envelope wages, unregistered employment, and kinship-based mutual aid, thereby enabling a robust assessment of their actual impact on Latvian society and socioeconomic stratification. The survey will allow for the identification of patterns in who participates in specific informal practices, how these practices intersect with experiences of exclusion or advantage, and how they may perpetuate or mitigate inequality.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

Survey data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

CSV

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

10

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

1.1.8 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")? Other relevant remarks)

The survey data might be useful for researchers studying shadow economy practices and inequality in economic sociology and anthropology, behavioral economics, and public policy. Moreover, the dataset can be used by policymakers and advisory organizations to gain insights on the complex relationship between inequality and shadow economy. Crucially, the quantitative data will provide a basis for cross-national and longitudinal comparisons, helping to situate Latvia within broader regional and global trends in informality and inequality.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

DDI (Data Documentation Initiative)

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

open (anyone is able to access data without restrictions)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

Yes

DataverseLV

2.2.4 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

The survey data will be stored in CSV format to ensure long-term usability. The data can be accessed and analyzed using commonly available statistical software such as R, Python, Stata, SPSS, or spreadsheet programs such as Microsoft Excel. No specialized or custom-built software will be required to access the archived dataset.

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

No

2.2.6 Is it possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?

No

2.3 Making data interoperable

2.3.1 Are the formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

The survey data will be stored in CSV format, which is a non-proprietary, open, and widely interoperable standard. CSV files can be accessed by a broad range of statistical and data-processing software, including R, Python, Stata, SPSS, and spreadsheet applications (e.g, Microsoft Excel).

2.3.2 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy to make your data interoperable?

No

2.4 Increase data re-use

2.4.1 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

2.4.5 Are data quality assurance processes provided?

No

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources

3.1.1 How will costs be covered for making data FAIR during project realization?

Euro

3.1.2 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

Andris Saulitis (0000-0002-5328-7645)

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Encryption
- Firewall
- Passwords

Data will be protected through a combination of password security, encryption, and physical access controls. All digital files will be stored on secure, password-protected systems, with access limited to authorized research team members. Strong, regularly updated passwords and, where possible, multi-factor authentication will be used to prevent unauthorized access. Data will be encrypted both in transit and at rest using industry-standard encryption protocols to ensure confidentiality.

Physical access to any devices or storage media containing survey data will be restricted to secure locations, such as locked offices or cabinets within controlled-access buildings. Only authorized personnel will have access to these spaces. Together, these measures ensure that survey data remain secure, confidential, and protected against unauthorized access or loss.

3.3 Ethical aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

No

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.3 Is informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data, if applicable?

No

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

Qualitative data

The qualitative data collected will consist of in-depth interviews, participant observation records, and detailed case studies documenting informal economic practices in Latvia. Fieldwork will be conducted in both urban and rural communities and will focus on practices such as envelope wages, unregistered employment, kinship-based mutual aid, and informal welfare arrangements. Interviews will explore participants' experiences, motivations, moral justifications, and perceptions of fairness, inequality, and state institutions.

In addition to interview transcripts and ethnographic fieldnotes, the project will generate systematically documented descriptions of specific informal practices. These qualitative materials will capture the social meanings, adaptive functions, and potential exclusionary effects of informality, providing contextual depth for understanding how such practices operate as both coping strategies and structural components of inequality.

Template: [LCS FARP](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Data Summary

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The qualitative data is gathered to explore the complex system of informal economic practices and inequality from a kinship perspective. The participant observation and interview data is intended to be analyzed along with the

nationally representative survey data in a mixed methods study that aims to explore informality, the associated social meanings, adaptive functions and exclusionary effects.

1.1.2 Type of data generated/collected

- Coded textual data
- Observation data

1.1.3 Format of data generated/collected

TXT

1.1.4 Expected size of the data – give expected size and choose unit of measurement

10

MB

1.1.5 Are you re-using this data set?

No

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

No

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

No

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

No

2.1.5 Will you follow any naming conventions for keywords?

No

2.1.6 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.2 Making data openly accessible

2.2.1 What type of access the data generated/produced will have (choose one)?

restricted, no access (access is denied, files will be opened only through contact person to the authors)

2.2.2 Will you apply embargo period to access for your data?

No

2.2.3 Will data, associated metadata, documentation and code be made accessible with means of a repository?

No

2.2.5 Will documentation about the software needed to access the data included?

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Yes

3.3.4 Will data collected/generated include personal data/ sensitive information?

No

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